

Need of Sustainable Agriculture Development in India

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Abstract

The Indian agriculture sector played a vital role in the development of the Indian economy. It can be seen through the contribution of gross domestic product and employment. The agriculture sector also contributes significantly to the sustainable economic development of India. The sustainable agricultural development of any country depends upon the careful use of its available natural resources. In spite of significant expansion in both the industrial and service sectors, agriculture remains the cornerstone of the Indian economy. This paper focuses on the issue of sustainable agricultural development in India.

Keywords: sustainable growth, resources, development, economy

Introduction

Sustainable agriculture development depends on three main goals: 1. ecological sustainability; 2. economic sustainability; and 3. social sustainability. In other words, sustainability rests on the principle that we must meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of upcoming generations to meet their own needs. Consequently, ownership of natural resources and human resources is of major importance. The rights of human resources include consideration of social responsibilities such as the working and living conditions of agriculturist families. The fundamental essential needs of rural communities, along with the health and safety of consumers, are critical considerations for both the present and future. Rights to land and natural resources include maintaining and enhancing this vital resource base for the long term.

The sustainable agricultural development of any country depends upon the careful use of its available natural resources. In 2011, India had 70% of its population live in rural areas. and agriculture as the main resource for its livelihood. In the last three decades, urbanization and industrialization have increased rapidly in India. And the size of agricultural land is decreasing. It is a major problem facing Indian agriculture. The main objective is to improve the productivity of agriculture. And it depends on increasing the area of cultivation, cropping patterns, and land productivity. Land productivity can be increased in two ways. The

first method is careful use of existing resources. The second method is increasing output by dividing the input. The first method is superior with respect to productivity and sustainability. But considering the increasing population of India, this method cannot provide a permanent solution. That is why we can go for the second method, which is harmful for the environment. And it also affects sustainability. Therefore, it is important to tackle the issues related to sustainable agriculture development.

- **Sustainable Agriculture Development**

Sustainable agriculture development should be discussed under three main types of farming systems. 1) Traditional agriculture method 2) modern agriculture method; and 3) sustainable agriculture method. Further, we have compared them across three dimensions: environmental sustainability, economic sustainability, and social sustainability.

- **Environmental Sustainability**

Traditional agricultural methods are harmful to the environment. It misuses natural resources. And it reduces soil fertility, causing soil erosion and contributing to global climate change. But sustainable agriculture has some major benefits over traditional agriculture methods.

- **Economic sustainability**

For agriculture to be sustainable, it must be economically feasible over a long period of time. Traditional agriculture methods include more economic risk than sustainable agriculture in the long run. Sustainable agriculture is important for meeting the domestic demand for food.

In India, more than 70% of the of the population lives in rural areas, and its main source of employment is agriculture and agriculture-allied activities. The traditional agriculture method cannot provide employment for the population. But sustainable agriculture development helps overcome these problems.

- **Social Sustainability**

Development cannot be sustainable unless it reduces poverty. Social sustainability in agriculture depends on the ideas of social acceptability and fairness. It is essential for the government to identify strategies that will allow the rural, impoverished population to gain advantages from agricultural development. That is why the sustainable agriculture method is useful to attain social sustainability.

Moreover, traditional agriculture methods are mainly based on labor-intensive techniques. And it is more gender-oriented, where women bear the heaviest burden of agriculture. Sustainable agriculture guarantees that both responsibilities and advantages are distributed fairly between men and women.

The traditional agriculture method is focused on a few food grains and commodities. And the traditional agriculture method faced the problem of low productivity. But sustainable agriculture methods improve the quality and nutritional value of food. And by producing a wider range of products, traditional agriculture methods are based on caste and wealth-oriented people. The richer and higher-caste people get, the more benefit. and the poor and lower castes are left out of the benefit. But the sustainable agriculture method attempts to ensure equal benefit.

- **Indian Agriculture**

In India, more than 75% of people live in rural areas. And about 42% of the geographical area is used for agricultural activities. The food grain production is 211 metric tons in the country. The Indian agriculture sector has become the world's largest producer of many commodities. Indian agriculture is an important producer of milk and dairy products, bananas, coconuts, mangoes, bananas, ginger, turmeric, cashew nuts, and pulses. Indian agriculture ranks as the second-largest producer of sugar, cotton, vegetables, rice, wheat, and fruits. And agriculture is one of the most important sectors in the Indian economy. Which provides income and employment to more than 70% of the population of the country.

The Government of India promotes sustainable agriculture policies under the 'National Mission of Sustainable Agriculture' (NMSA). The existing efforts, like increasing soil productivity, increasing water

efficiency, etc., are meant to minimize the risk to the agriculture sector. Sustainable agriculture development helps to maintain environmental health and also increases economic profitability.

• **Issues and Challenges**

The main issue in sustainable agricultural development is the essential to increase productivity food grain, create employment, and deliver a source of permanent income source to the poor population in the country. The step of acceptance of advanced agriculture technology in India is very slow. The agriculture performance is unplanned and unscientific. Some of the basic issues for development of Indian agriculture sector are to develop the sufficient source of finance, to develop cooperative institutions, to increase the agro based research centers.

Conclusion

Agricultural technology must be transformed from production to profit - oriented sustainable farming. It is important to create the healthy environment for the adoption of sustainable agriculture method. To create new opportunities for agriculture farmers, workers, researchers, and policy makers to use new technology. To increase agro related businesses, like dairy farming, poultry farming and fisheries. And all of these practices not only for their economic development but also as the basis for further intensification and ecological sustainability. To conclude, natural farm management to improve productivity, profitability and sustainability of the farming system will go a long way to ensure all round sustainability.

References

1. Ruddar Datt & Sundharam (2014), "Indian Economy", S. Chand & Co. Ltd; New Delhi.
2. David, T., Cassman, K. G., Matson, P. A., Naylor, R. and Polasky,S., (2002) Agricultural sustainability and intensive production practices. *Nature*
3. Schiere, J. B., Ibrahim, M. N. M. and van Keulen, H. (2002), The role of livestock for sustainability in mixed farming: criteria and scenario studies under varying resource allocation. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.*
4. Dev, S. Mahendra (2008) Inclusive Growth in India, Agriculture, Poverty and Human Development, Oxford University Press, New Delhi
5. Gupta, A.K. (1990) Sustainable Development of Indian Agriculture
6. Greenpeace India (2007), "Hiding Behind the Poor", Bangalore.
7. Kohli, K., Menon, M., Das, S., and Badami, D., (2009): "Calling the Bluff: Revealing the State of Monitoring and Compliance of Environmental Clearance www.agriculture.gov.in